

INTENSE DENOTATION OF ALEKSANDR FAYNBERG'S POEMS

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Annotation: *When we read Feinberg's poems about the homeland, patriotism immediately comes to light towards to our country, as his poems not only describe what Tashkent looked like in the post-war periods. But also send an invisible message how merciful are uzbek people and praise Tashkent which gave lodging for his parents . And accepted as own son.*

Key words: *Denotation , stylistics , poetic*

Feinberg wrote seven scripts for feature films. By the decree of the President of Russia, the People's Poet of Uzbekistan Alexander Arkadyevich Fainberg was awarded the Pushkin Medal . For several years, A. A. Fainberg led a seminar for young writers of Uzbekistan in Tashkent. He was also a member of the Union of Writers of Uzbekistan.

A brilliant translator, Feinberg opened many works of famous Uzbek poets to the Russian-speaking reader. Erkin Vakhidov's poem "The Revolt of the Immortals" was published in Moscow, and the collection "Swan Flock" was published in Tashkent - translations of poems by Abdulla Aripov and Khosiyat Rustamova, Sirojiddin Said and Omon Matchon. It is noteworthy that the poems of the poet himself were translated into Uzbek and published in the collection "Chigir". There is a lot of sparkling humor in Feinberg's poems. In the poem "The String of Rubayat" he described the Uzbek teahouse with the same pilaf with such gaiety that one cannot read without a smile.

He was awarded by the president of Uzbekistan for a significant contribution to strengthening the independence of the Motherland, increasing the international prestige of the country, the growth of culture and spirituality of our people, for nationwide recognition and respect won by unique talent, multifaceted creativity, scientific activity, many years of fruitful work in the field of science, education, literature, culture, art , healthcare, sports and other social spheres, for active participation in public life.

The well-known People's Poet of Uzbekistan, A. Feinberg's colleague in the writing workshop, translator A. Aripov rightly noted that truly talented people do not belong to any one people.

They are the property of all mankind, because, like stars in the sky, they shine for everyone, reflecting the deepest human feelings and eternal enduring values that nourish the Soul.

They are able to embody this living, subtle, sharply reacting to everything that happens around the human Soul in an exact poetic word. A. Feinberg is a poetic phenomenon, a symbol of the era, a multifaceted, deep, multi-level poet, the comprehension and awareness of which is yet to be read by readers, literary critics and the poets themselves.

Fainberg was sure that "initially, the poet or artist who says that I did it is wrong. Yes, he did nothing, it was transmitted from above through him, as through a singing reed. This is not a merit, but a gift from God, for which we must thank fate. Who am i? I don't know what will be written in the next line. Poetry is a God-given song."Everything that the poet touched, whether it be "free sonnets", rubaiyat, poems "The String of the Rubaiyat", "The String of the Buffoon" or in content and form "The Poet's Farewell", was so incomparable in its stylistic manner in terms of content, strophic, rhythm and other elements of versification, that they open up boundless spaces for future researchers.

In the poems of Alexander Feinberg, from simple human feelings, to the problems of the universe. He is the pure, noble manto preserve their feelings, to save human nature and the world from crisisencourages. The well-being of the world, the happiness of man is the society in which he livesis integral to its development. When others are happy, I am unhappyI can't, I can't be happy when others are unhappy.To all members of the society for solidarity and solidarity for the development of the Motherland

happy when I'm in a hurry,
Don't hang out with friends when I'm singing -
Someone's pain won't leave me,
I'm suffering from anxiety.
If I suddenly feel sad in life,
I'm in a hurry to put an end to jealousy and betrayal -
Someone's joy makes me happy,
Happiness is someone who can't stop crying.

In changing one's worldview, one has to understand oneself, consciously in encouraging them to live, making the younger generation a perfect human beingin

upbringing, how many poems by a poet like Alexander Feinberg enrich our spirituality important.

There is a poem by Alexander Feinberg called "Eleven-meter penalty kick".

It depicts a football field game and a goalkeeper. The gate in the poem-Homeland, football team - the people, the goalkeeper - the inviolability of the homeland, the people is depicted as a guard of honor and freedom. In it the poet with all his skill. I hung like a lock on the gate. I shot like a ball at every kick - says the goalkeeper. Eleven meters into the goal due to a mistake by the defender a penalty kick is awarded. "I don't understand why our defender fell in vain "The ninth," reads the goalkeeper. This is a football game report or is a live image, not a comment. He's on the field, fighting, face to face with the striker.

I went out with the Ninth.

He came running...

The ball is kicked, it's heavy!

Oh, how angry he is!

I threw the ball into the air.

I'd like to have a shave

Zafar sang like a trumpet.

The lines are written in parts, the tone of the goalkeeper is intense shows the movement. In the poem, the goalkeeper's mental state, suffering, dreams and the joy is skillfully captured.

What do I need attacking fame for?

I never score a goal.

Self-sacrificing,

I'm honest with my team.

There is no such thing as a selfless, brave and courageous goalkeeper the attacker cannot achieve his goal. In these life games, fierce attackers, referees, not cheating players, but strong-willed guards The poem ends with a logical and beautiful conclusion that he can win.

the grandeur of our people, the hospitality, the homes of the people in the villages

that he never locks the doors, and that the table is always open

affects. Human, like Uzbek generosity, trust and devotion

the feeling is unique and unique all over the world, in front of such a country is

Europe

nothing, says the poet. And so proud of the existence of the Motherland. That's

it

I am an integral part of the homeland, a small part of such a great country Europe, ya vas ne znayu. This is the poet's confession. I am from Uzbekistan, my roots are here, other country is like Uzbekistan to me Alexander Faynberg is reluctant to say that he cannot be kind and precious. Feinberg, a brilliant translator, has revealed to the Russian-speaking reader many works by well-known Uzbek poets.

Feinberg's poems have a spark of humor. In the epic "Ruboiy tori", he described the constant change of the Uzbek teahouse through laughter in such a way that it is impossible to read it without a smile on the face.

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